

Thematic differences by gender in the field of Library and Information Science from 2017 to 2021

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Abstract

It is known that women researchers are a minority in the workforce and in scientific production. Moreover, the disparity is even greater when looking at specific fields. Several studies have addressed the gender gap and detected that the perceived impact for female authors is lower than their male peers. This difference may be related to structural factors and its basis is unclear. The current study performs a co-words science mapping analysis to find out the differences and similarities in the themes covered by female and male authors, in the field of Library and Information Science in the period 2017-2021, and to detect differences in citation impact, in order to expose if these disparities are due to themes differences. The results showed that female authors are more inclined to work on themes related to health and people, and those themes proved to obtain a low performance, while male authors address different themes and many of them are related to STEM, which influences their impact. The analysis shows that the themes addressed by the male authors demonstrated to have more impact on the scientific community than the themes addressed by female authors.

Introduction

Despite many efforts have been made in recent years for equality in the scientific workforce, the gender gap remains (Huang, Gates, Sinatra, & Barabási, 2020; Lariviere, Ni, Gingras, Cronin, & Sugimoto, 2013). In 2019, women represented just 29,3% of all researchers worldwide and this scenario does not change from a local perspective (UNESCO, 2019). Consequently, men are producing more and having more impact than their female peers (Zhang, Sivertsen, Du, Huang, & Glänzel, 2021). In scientific careers, this disparity has consequences for the receipt of funding (Boekhout, Van der Weijden, & Waltman, 2021), economic income (Moss-Racusin, Dovidio, Brescoll, Graham, & Handelsman, 2012), career trajectories (Cech & Blair-Loy, 2019), salary gap (European Commission & Directorate-General for Communication, 2020) and finally, hiring (Shen, 2013). To improve this context, Europe turned this problem into a governmental plan, which aimed to promote gender equality and to address emerging issues, such as gender perspective in climate change, online violence against women and artificial intelligence (European Commission, 2016).

In fact, meanwhile, there are more graduate and undergraduate women than men in most countries (OECD, 2022), women are also under-represented in science, and in some fields, the gender gap is even wider. In science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) the gender disparity is noticeable (Eaton, Saunders, Jacobson, & West, 2020), although, the scenario changes through different fields and subfields (Cheryan, Ziegler, Montoya, & Jiang, 2017). In general, the female workforce is similar in people and health-related fields (Boekhout

et al., 2021). The causes of this unequal participation in scientific production are unclear. The debate revolves around structural issues caused by the functioning of current society and the gender roles associated with men and women (Kozłowski, Larivière, Sugimoto, & Monroe-White, 2022; Petrongolo, 2019). These problems are related to housework, care, and unequal sharing of tasks, for example.

Accordingly, if we can measure the gender disparity in qualitative and quantitative terms, it would be possible to act on the problem and maybe alleviate it. In that way, bibliometrics is an interesting field of study that allows the use of different tools to measure the science, and it has been used to reveal those disparities. It applies statistical methods to analyze quantitatively the scientific production and the research impact (Gutiérrez-Salcedo, Martínez, Moral-Munoz, Herrera-Viedma, & Cobo, 2018; Halevi, 2019). Different studies showed that the male authors have been overrepresented in some fields (Huang et al., 2020; Joanis & Patil, 2022; Kwiek & Roszka, 2021, 2022; Ni, Smith, Yuan, Larivière, & Sugimoto, 2021) and have more impact than their peers (Ghiasi, Mongeon, Sugimoto, & Larivière, 2018). The pattern in mobility in the scientific career is also different by gender (Zhao, Aref, Zagheni, & Stecklov, 2022) and the minority groups have disadvantages to be in the scientific community (Kozłowski et al., 2022).

This scenario is composed of different actors, variables, and events. In relation to this, the 'science of science' can know the evolution of science and find behavioral patterns (Fortunato et al., 2018). Using different statistical, complex systems, artificial intelligence, and machine learning methods to manipulate *Big Data* it is possible to generate scientific maps to understand the conceptual, social and intellectual structure of the scientific production (Cobo, López-Herrera, Herrera-Viedma, & Herrera, 2011a). Thus, the understanding of the themes covered by each gender can facilitate the understanding of these dynamics in science and how the actors involved participate. This act can guide the future of the scientific world toward a more inclusive space.

In this sense, the main aim of this contribution is to analyze the conceptual differences in the research carried out by female and male researchers, in order to determine if this could be one of the causes of the disparity in their academic impact. To do that, the field of Library and Information Science (LIS) in the period 2017-2022 was analyzed, in order to study the gender differences in the last years. The corpus was divided into two different datasets containing articles in which, on the one hand, most of the authors are female and, on the other hand, most of the authors are male. For each dataset, a strategic diagram showing the themes was built, also adding quantitative and impact measures. In addition, the themes covered in the whole dataset were also uncovered to compare the global landscape with the gender specific one.

This contribution is organized as follows. Firstly, the Methodology section describes the main steps carried out in this contribution. Then, the Results section presents the analysis, strategic diagrams, and main performance tables. Later, Discussion section explains and contextualizes the results obtained. Finally, the conclusions are drafted.

Methodology

This section is dedicated to describing the methodology used to analyze gender differences in the LIS field. In this way, the methodology prepares the dataset and generates a set of scientific maps.

The corpus was retrieved from the Web of Science. The criteria adopted were the following:

- Documents indexed on the Science Citation Index™ Expanded (SCI) or Social Sciences Citation Index® (SSCI).
- Documents under the “Information Science & Library Science” category.
- Documents produced between 2017 and 2021.
- Documents tagged as articles or reviews.

Specifically, the advanced query used to obtain the data from the Web of Science database was $WC = (\text{“Information Science \& Library Science”}) \text{ AND } DT = (\text{Article OR Review}) \text{ AND } FPY = (2017-2021)$. The query was performed on 20 September 2022 and retrieved an amount of 23,199 documents.

To conduct the bibliometric analysis, the open-source software SciMAT was used. This tool employs science mapping analysis approaches, improving the interpretation of aspects of the bibliometric network (Cobo et al., 2011a; Cobo, López-Herrera, Herrera-Viedma, & Herrera, 2011b). One of the advantages of using this tool is the capability to detect themes from the keywords of the corpus and plot them in the strategic diagram. This technique facilitates the understanding and interpretation of the themes covered by the database of the documents analyzed.

The next step is to pre-process the keywords by doing the de-duplication step. This stage consists of joining the keywords used to describe the same concept and determining which terms have a broad meaning.

Once this process is done, it is necessary to identify the gender of each author. The gender was assigned using the given name of each author. Three databases containing given name and gender were used to perform this step: the Census of United States (U.S. Social Security Administration., 2020), the python library GenderGuesser (Pérez, 2016), and the repository NamesDatabase (Leaderboard, 2022). For unisex names, a disambiguation algorithm was used, that assigns the more probable gender to the given name. We should remark that gender was considered binary because other genders can only be assigned by self-identification.

Since our main goal is to determine the differences between the research conducted by female and male researchers, our dataset was divided into the following ones:

- Papers in which most of the authors are female (more than 50% of the authors are female).
- Papers in which most of the authors are male (more than 50% of the authors are male).
- Also, we consider the global dataset.

The next step performed was the building of the co-word networks using the author’s keywords of each document. That is, each dataset is modeled as a network where the nodes represent the keywords, and the edges represent a co-occurrence relationship among them (the linked keywords appeared together in at least one document).

Later, a normalization process was performed in the co-occurrence frequency by means of the equivalence index (Cobo et al., 2011a; Eck & Waltman, 2009). This is a key step to avoid biases in the networks. Next, the community detection was performed using the *Leiden clustering algorithm* (Traag, Waltman, & van Eck, 2019). The selection of this algorithm was based on the guarantees of well-connected communities (Traag et al., 2019). The community detection gives us a set of clusters, representing the themes or topics covered in each specific dataset. The

name of each theme is given by the most central keywords of the subnetwork associated with it.

These themes represent a set of research topics covered by the field and are visually represented by a strategic diagram, which is a two-dimensional representation based on the centrality and density measures of each theme. The centrality measure indicates the external cohesion of the community and represents its relation with other communities, while the density reveals the internal cohesion and represents how the keywords describing each community are related (Cahlik, 2000; Cobo et al., 2011a). In this way, themes can be classified in four categories: motor, basic, isolated, or emergent/declining. A theme considered as motor, where the centrality and density are high, evidences its central position in relation to other themes covered by the field, and that the keywords included in this community present a high cohesion rate. It is interpreted as a developed and well-structured theme with great importance for the research field. Similarly, highly developed and isolated themes present weak relations between other communities, although high density among the keywords in the community, representing specialized or peripheral themes. Themes classified as emerging or declining do not present a strong centrality in the research field, and their internal cohesion is not high, suggesting disappearing or emerging themes. Finally, basic, and transversal themes represent themes that have high importance to the field for their centrality, although are low develop, showing transversal and general themes.

After community detection, the indicators of academic impact can be calculated. The measures computed were the number of documents, the citation average, the mean normalized citation score (MNCS) (Waltman, van Eck, van Leeuwen, Visser, & van Raan, 2011), the documents in the 1% of most cited papers and H-Classic, the percentage of gender in the theme, and the percentage of gender in the global dataset.

Results

Descriptive analysis

The global dataset was retrieved using the advanced query described in the Methodology section. It recovered 23,199 documents authored by 48,120 researchers. After gender assignment, 16,822 (34.96%) authors were assigned as female, 19,578 (40.68%) as male, and 11,720 (24.36%) as unknown. Table 1 shows some descriptive statistics that summarize the three datasets.

Table 1: Descriptive analysis of total, most female and most male datasets.

<i>Metrics</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Male</i>
H-index	135	68	94
Citations (geometric mean)	11.36	7.69	13.11
Citations (standard deviation)	25.37	15.74	32.87
Citations (median)	5	3	5
%Documents	100%	24.3%	32.8%
Number of documents	23,199	5,635	7,616

Whole dataset – conceptual analysis

The strategic diagram generated by the global dataset (Figure 1) identified 30 themes and, according to Table 2, only the themes *Health care*, *Interviews* and *Academic libraries* show a higher concentration of female authors than male authors. *Health care* is a theme related to medical care in different areas, i.e., it analyzes the disease, but also the patient experience and

the community support. The theme *Interviews* is associated with research design, quantitative analysis, and the narratives themselves. Finally, *Academic libraries*, a classic theme in LIS, is related to information literacy, public libraries, and library management. The first two are positioned as motor and the last one as basic and transversal. All three are central themes in the field, although just the last one is general and transversal, it is interesting to note, for the three themes mentioned that the geometric mean of citations is low when compared to other identified themes. Something similar occurs with the percentage of documents in the 1% of most cited papers and H-Classic. As for MNCS, *Health care* is the only one of these three themes that achieve the global mean of citations in LIS, both *Interviews* and *Academic libraries* remain with values below 1.

In contrast, male authors have a better distribution across different themes. That is, there are few themes in which men are not the majority. Precisely, in the themes *Machine learning*, *Privacy*, *Bibliometrics* and *Digital divide* a gender imbalance is observed. The *Machine learning* covers different topics related to artificial intelligence, data mining and natural language processing. Moreover, the *Privacy* deals with topics related to Big Data surveillance and blockchain. *Bibliometrics*, a classic theme in LIS, is related to citation analysis, research evaluation and scientific collaboration. Finally, the *Digital divide* is concerned with analysing digital inequalities, developing countries and competition. The first three are positioned as basic and transversal, while *Digital divide* is positioned as an emerging theme, representing its novelty as a theme covered by LIS nowadays. Regarding these themes, the geometric mean of citations, in general, is higher than the themes in which women are the majority. Likewise, for *Privacy*, *Machine learning* and *Digital divide* the MNCS exceed the global mean of citations. The percentage of documents in the calculated impact indicators is high and reaches up to 25% in the case of *Privacy*.

Figure 1: Strategic diagram of documents of the global dataset.

Covid-19 is an interesting health-related theme that is worth mentioning, which is related to different domains of the pandemic, as well as public health, misinformation, and telemedicine. Interestingly, despite being a health-related theme, there is a global balance between men and women and the performance indicators are much more competitive than those obtained by *Health care*. It is important to note that even when men are involved in a health-related field, as in the case of *Covid-19*, there is a high number of citations per document compared to other themes.

In summary, what was observed in the identified themes in the global strategic diagram is that the female authors are concentrated on themes that receive low citations rates, the documents do not usually obtain a high impact and, in addition, the MNCS obtained oscillate between 0.7 and 1. Meanwhile, the male authors are more distributed by themes covering several fields of study in which the citation rates and the percentage of impact vary.

Table 2: Performance analysis of the global dataset.

<i>Theme</i>	Σ Docs.	Σ Citations	Citations (gmean)	MNCS	%Docs. (1%)	%Docs. (H-Classic)	%F	%M	%U	%F (Global)	%M (Global)	%U (Global)
SMALL-AND-MEDIUM-PRIVACY	779	18283	11.87	2.090	12.07	11.72	25.8	47.9	26.3	4.5	6.6	6.4
SHARING-ECONOMY	1424	30579	9.77	2.042	25.43	20.98	25.6	48.4	26.0	8.1	12.8	12.9
COVID-19	152	3697	11.11	2.005	2.16	1.91	18.2	54.8	27.0	0.7	1.5	1.4
MACHINE-LEARNING	872	13436	7.00	1.910	12.5	9.54	35.0	45.2	19.8	8.1	8.6	6.7
SATISFACTION	2115	35273	8.50	1.595	19.4	20.44	22.8	43.7	33.5	13.1	20.3	24.7
DIGITAL-DIVIDE	715	12651	9.95	1.555	5.17	5.99	25.2	38.8	36.0	4.2	4.9	7.4
SELF-DETERMINATION-THEORY	1260	21154	8.83	1.465	14.22	11.17	25.8	46.6	27.7	8.1	10.8	10.5
KNOWLEDGE-MANAGEMENT	334	5730	8.60	1.456	1.72	3.27	29.3	43.9	26.7	2.4	3.0	3.1
RECOMMENDER-SYSTEMS	1526	24235	8.30	1.373	10.78	10.63	30.0	45.2	24.8	10.1	11.7	12.0
E-GOVERNMENT	207	3404	9.17	1.370	1.29	1.36	13.6	46.8	39.6	0.7	1.9	2.4
SOCIAL-MEDIA	1188	17590	7.72	1.349	7.76	6.81	32.0	44.1	23.9	7.9	9.0	8.0
INFORMATION-SECURITY	2620	41213	8.16	1.348	15.09	17.98	30.1	43.1	26.7	15.9	18.0	20.0
INFORMATION-RETRIEVAL	200	3119	9.09	1.281	0.43	0.54	21.9	54.2	24.0	1.4	2.1	1.6
SMARTPHONE	519	7610	6.00	1.265	4.74	5.45	32.8	44.9	22.3	4.3	4.5	3.9
ELECTRONIC-HEALTH-RECORDS	336	4865	8.21	1.224	1.72	1.91	29.8	46.1	24.1	2.6	3.1	2.5
ORGANIZATIONAL-HEALTH-CARE	1088	15640	7.12	1.180	5.17	4.63	39.0	44.4	16.6	15.8	14.1	9.3
BIBLIOMETRICS	369	4363	6.12	1.044	1.29	0.82	40.1	44.3	15.6	3.2	2.8	2.1
INEQUALITY	1834	21163	6.52	1.013	6.47	7.08	48.4	35.7	15.8	24.4	13.8	10.6
INTERVIEWS	2734	29527	6.01	0.913	8.62	7.63	24.4	50.0	25.6	13.0	17.9	18.1
INDICATORS	621	6051	6.22	0.904	2.16	1.36	42.7	40.0	17.2	7.7	5.3	4.1
JOURNALISM	469	4929	6.92	0.842	0.86	0.82	58.0	31.0	11.0	8.4	3.3	2.1
DIVERSITY	425	4072	5.40	0.831	1.29	1.09	31.5	50.9	17.7	3.2	3.7	2.3
INFORMATION-BEHAVIOR	886	8388	4.90	0.814	3.45	3	35.6	45.6	18.8	6.3	6.3	5.1
CLASSIFICATION	708	6583	4.89	0.772	1.72	1.63	40.5	39.9	19.7	6.5	5.4	4.1
ACADEMIC-LIBRARIES	704	5916	5.31	0.770	0.86	1.63	36.9	40.3	22.8	5.7	4.8	5.0
OPEN-ACCESS	719	6101	4.57	0.744	1.72	1.63	35.0	46.9	18.1	4.8	4.7	3.9
COLLABORATION	2164	17231	4.58	0.729	5.17	5.99	42.0	36.0	22.0	17.0	11.9	13.2
ONTOLOGY	857	6583	4.89	0.694	0.86	0.54	33.8	45.6	20.6	5.6	5.8	4.8
	998	7726	4.49	0.657	1.72	2.18	41.7	40.0	18.3	8.7	6.7	5.5
	367	1984	3.60	0.440	0	0	31.7	44.7	23.6	2.4	3.0	2.6

Most female – conceptual analysis

The strategic diagram generated by the dataset of documents in which most authors were female (Figure 2) identified 11 themes, and Table 3 shows the performance indicators obtained. It is important to note that 10 of these themes are similar to those reported in the global strategic diagram, and the theme *Smart City* is the only one that corresponds exclusively to the female analysis. The *Smart City* theme is related to information management, well-being, citizen participation and sustainability. This theme is one of those with the lowest number of documents and is positioned as a motor theme, which represents its strong centrality and development between the themes covered by the female authors. The geometric mean of citations obtained is around the intermediate values obtained by the themes of the global diagram. Meanwhile, the MNCS observed in this theme is the second highest of the female themes. Despite this, the percentage of *Smart City* documents in the 1% of the most cited papers and H-Classic is almost zero.

Analyzing the theme *Health care* in the female diagram, although the geometric mean of citation is lower than that obtained by the global dataset, the MNCS achieved is higher. Nevertheless, the pattern of lower documents in the impact indicators computed is also reported. For the theme *Interviews*, the scenario of the geometric mean of citation and MNCS are similar, while the percentage of documents in both the H-Classic and the 1% of the most cited papers is slightly higher.

These results confirm the findings obtained before, although female authors are distributed in different themes, there is a tendency to research on themes with the lowest performance indicators.

Figure 2: Strategic diagram of documents in which most of the authors are female.

Table 3: Performance analysis of the dataset in which most authors are female.

<i>Theme</i>	$\sum \text{Docs.}$	$\sum \text{Citations}$	<i>Citations (gmean)</i>	<i>MNCS</i>	<i>%Docs. (1%)</i>	<i>%Docs. (H-Classic)</i>	<i>%F</i>	<i>%M</i>	<i>%U</i>	<i>%F (Global)</i>	<i>%M (Global)</i>	<i>%U (Global)</i>
SOCIAL-MEDIA	639	7253	6.40	1.686	4.31	2.45	86.6	11.1	2.3	24.7	24.9	23.4
SMART-CITY	141	1457	6.84	1.602	0.43	0.27	85.8	11.6	2.6	6.1	5.1	7.1
ELECTRONIC-HEALTH-RECORDS	331	3669	6.08	1.543	1.72	1.09	81.3	14.8	3.9	16.9	23.9	27.9
INTERVIEWS	373	3833	6.25	1.399	2.16	1.09	84.8	12.1	3.1	19.9	18.8	23.0
HEALTH-CARE	615	6051	5.95	1.260	2.59	1.63	86.6	11.3	2.1	30.6	26.4	26.0
INEQUALITY	163	1554	6.65	1.176	0	0	86.8	9.8	3.4	9.0	7.8	11.5
ORGANIZATIONAL-COMMUNICATION	229	1980	4.88	1.161	0.86	0.82	86.7	10.8	2.6	9.5	8.8	7.8
OPEN-ACCESS	254	1797	4.50	0.920	0	0.27	87.9	10.2	2.0	8.6	8.3	8.6
DIVERSITY	112	538	3.22	0.693	0	0	88.0	9.6	2.5	4.6	3.8	3.0
ACADEMIC-LIBRARIES	656	3166	3.63	0.627	0.43	0.27	90.6	8.0	1.5	23.6	16.8	14.9
COLLABORATION	317	1611	3.81	0.624	0	0	89.5	8.7	1.8	11.7	10.2	9.3

Most male – conceptual analysis

Figure 3 shows the 16 themes identified in the dataset in which most of the authors were male, and as shown in Table 4, 13 of the identified themes are similar to the clusters detected in the global dataset. The *Blockchain*, *Innovation*, and *Information seeking* are themes exclusively detected by the male diagram. The *Blockchain* theme is related to information systems, cryptocurrencies, and smart contracts. Then, *Innovation* theme deals with topics related to patents, technology, and complexity. Lastly, the *Information seeking* theme is associated with information management, information seeking behavior, and information needs.

Figure 3: Strategic diagram of documents in which most of the authors are male.

Among these three exclusively male themes, there is a large fluctuation of values in the performance indicators. *Blockchain* receives the highest geometric mean of citations by far, gets three times the global mean of citations in LIS and has more than 5% of the documents in the 1% of the most cited papers and H-Classics. This theme is positioned between the motor and highly developed and isolated themes, showing its strong centrality and development, although it confirms to be highly specialized. Meanwhile, *Information seeking* theme receives half the geometric mean of *Blockchain* citations, the MNCS is a quarter of *Blockchain* MNCS and is positioned as a motor theme.

In the male diagram, the theme *Machine learning* has both the geometric mean of citations and MNCS similar to the theme *Machine learning* located in the global diagram. By contrast, the percentage of documents in the impact indicators is 7%, while this value in the global diagram is around 19%. For *Covid-19* theme, the scenario changes, when this theme was identified on the male diagram, the geometric mean of citations and MNCS were higher. When analyzing the percentage of documents in the 1% of most cited papers and H-Classic this value drops to half. These results lead us to interpret that male authors are more evenly distributed among the themes, addressing themes that could have a high impact on performance. Although they are also engaging in themes whose performance is not especially high. These events confirm the

hypothesis that the impact obtained by each gender could be affected by the themes covered by each of them.

Table 4: Performance analysis of the dataset in which most of the authors are male authors.

Σ Docs.	Σ Citations	Citations (gmean)	MNCS	%Docs. (1%)	%Docs. (H- Classic)	%F	%M	%U	%F (Global)	%M (Global)	%U (Global)
162	5671	11.95	3.311	6.9	5.18	6.5	86.7	6.8	2.9	4.9	6.6
270	5980	8.35	2.281	5.6	4.36	8.9	86.0	5.1	9.5	9.1	9.3
343	7899	9.26	1.595	2.59	2.45	16.0	76.7	7.3	23.0	14.4	19.3
765	14485	8.97	1.535	7.76	7.36	9.7	83.8	6.5	22.6	24.5	27.6
275	5579	9.43	1.496	3.88	3.27	7.3	86.7	6.0	4.6	7.3	7.4
476	9475	10.74	1.435	4.74	4.36	10.5	85.4	4.1	11.0	12.3	9.3
392	6421	8.67	1.324	2.59	3	8.1	87.4	4.6	9.2	10.9	9.3
803	13106	8.47	1.226	4.31	5.45	8.8	86.7	4.5	15.8	19.3	15.6
156	2421	8.00	1.199	1.72	0.82	7.7	89.1	3.2	3.0	3.8	2.6
1078	14806	6.59	1.000	6.9	4.09	7.6	88.5	3.9	18.4	21.7	18.3
189	1963	5.67	0.865	0.43	0.82	5.7	90.9	3.4	3.0	4.5	2.6
196	1741	5.14	0.763	0.43	0.54	6.9	87.8	5.3	4.3	5.0	5.3
229	2100	4.15	0.719	0.86	0.82	7.5	90.1	2.4	4.2	4.7	2.6
213	1805	5.43	0.716	0.43	0.27	8.2	89.0	2.8	4.7	4.7	3.7
227	1897	5.02	0.667	0.43	0.27	7.5	89.4	3.0	4.3	5.1	3.6
155	1179	4.59	0.551	0	0	7.5	88.3	4.1	3.6	3.9	3.1

<i>Theme</i>
BLOCKCHAIN
COVID-19
ELECTRONIC-HEALTH-RECORDS
MACHINE-LEARNING
E-GOVERNMENT
KNOWLEDGE-MANAGEMENT
PRIVACY
SOCIAL-MEDIA
INNOVATION
BIBLIOMETRICS
DIGITAL-DIVIDE
INFORMATION-SEEKING
CLASSIFICATION
OPEN-ACCESS
INDICATORS
ONTOLOGY

Discussion

Once the results were presented, an exploration of the themes covered by the strategic diagrams and their impacts were given. Responding to the aim of this contribution, we found that the impact of the scientific production in LIS authored by females is lower than their male peers. In that way, this global finding is in line with those previously reported by different studies, showing this gender disparity in scientific performance (Abramo, Cicero, & D'Angelo, 2015; Mauleón & Bordons, 2006; Zhang et al., 2021).

Thus, the global strategic diagram showed that the female authors are more gender-balanced in themes that receive a lower geometric mean of citation. Meanwhile, the men authors are spread in different fields of study and a fluctuation in the geometric mean of citation is observed. This information is crucial to understand the impact perceived by the different genders.

The strategic diagram of most female authors revealed that the themes most addressed by women are related to fields associated with health and people, and these themes achieve lower performance indicators than the themes related to other fields. As previous studies indicated, women are underrepresented in fields related to science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (Ceci, Ginther, Kahn, & Williams, 2014). In STEM, some fields are more gender-balanced than others and computer science is one of them (Ceci et al., 2014; Cheryan et al., 2017). This gap has no foundation on biological bases and suggests strong environmental factors (Ceci et al., 2014; Kowal, Sorokowski, Kulczycki, & Żelaźniewicz, 2022). Consequently, it is fundamental to take into consideration that characteristics like race and ethnicity represent additional challenges for female authors (Kozłowski et al., 2022).

Interestingly, the diagram in which most of the authors were female exposes that in the period analyzed, the women authors are exploring the theme *Smart City*. This observation suggests that women authors are represented in some fields of STEM as mentioned by Cheryan et al. (2017). Nonetheless, despite efforts, cities of today continue to reflect the sided perspective of able-bodied, heterosexual, cis-gender men and the consequence of this is the perpetuation of gender disparities and other types of inequality (Calvi, 2022). This view can improve and continue the discussion trough of women in Urban land science. The last is an emerging interdisciplinary field that analyzes the diversity of urban issues. In this area, the gender gap is not very pronounced, but the gap in female production and impact is real (Chen & Seto, 2022). When looking at the *Smart city* theme in the female diagram, it is possible to deduce that the greater presence of women can influence the increase of productivity in themes related to smart cities. Therefore, women, as users and/or developers, who experience the problems of cities

and specifically issues caused by urbanization can visualize a city with different perspectives and create a more inclusive one (Chang, Choi, An, & Chung, 2022).

In contrast to the themes in which most of the authors were female, the diagram in which most of the authors were male revealed that the themes covered by men achieve, in general, more relevant indicators of performance. The subjects covered by the themes are various, although many of them could be related to STEM and more specifically to computer science. These topics could represent different types of challenges for the scientist; however, they are considered disruptive and could receive more attention from the research community. In fact, it is interesting to note that the MNCS and the geometric mean of citations obtained by these fields are, in general, higher than the MNCS obtained by people-related fields.

An interesting theme to analyze in the diagram which most of the authors were male is *Innovation*. Innovation is defined as an application of a new or significantly improved method or technique. Therefore, this type of scientific production might have more impact on the research community than typical scientific contributions. In the actual study, *Innovation* has an impact highest than the global mean of citations in LIS, and about 1,5% of papers in impact indicators, H-Classic and 1% of most cited papers. This suggests that the dedication to something linked to innovation could affect positively the impact perceived by the authors. In addition, the coronavirus pandemic was an event that occurred to all authors in the database, although it was experienced by each community differently. The variables of gender, social class and how each country managed the pandemic, for example, influenced how this period affected each person's life. Unfortunately, this crisis makes the gender gap even wider. The production of female authors was affected by childcare and household care (Lamarre, 2020; Liu et al., 2022; Reichelt, Makovi, & Sargsyan, 2021). In the global and in which most of the authors were male diagrams, the theme *Covid-19* was identified as a motor theme, demonstrating its strong centrality and the high development in this field. That suggests that the male authors were the leading producer of Covid-19 content during the pandemic. Even the papers with most male authors perceived a higher MNCS if compared with the papers with both genders type of representation, this fact may also affect the impact perceived by the male authors.

Accordingly, the results reported by this work showed that some themes are more related to single-gender authors. Despite this, some studies have shown that diversity in gender, nationality, and team size improves the impact and the innovation of the scientific output (Hofstra et al., 2020; Larivière, Gingras, Sugimoto, & Tsou, 2015; Murray et al., 2018). Consequently, more diverse participation in the production of academic studies is needed to ensure that science is being created including different perspectives and is as inclusive as possible.

Although the findings showed in this research, it is important to report some limitations. The analysis was performed using the Web of Science database in the specific period of 2017-2021 and the amount of unidentified gender was around 24%. The main reasons for the high number of unidentified genders in the study were the presence of non-Occidental first names and the absence of first names for some authors. This was due to the fact that the three databases used in the study contained first name and gender information that primarily reflected Occidental culture, making it difficult to accurately identify the rest of authors. On the other hand, it should be highlighted that only the last five years have been analyzed because our goal is the describe the current state of gender inequalities in the LIS field. In future research, other bibliographic databases will be included with a larger period to get information about the temporal and

structural situation of LIS as a field, and a remodeled methodology will be used to improve gender assignation.

Conclusions

This contribution presents the similarities and differences between female and male researchers in the LIS research area, during the period 2017-2021. As shown, the themes covered by most women authors are related to health and people and present a low number of citations and few documents in 1% of most cited papers and H-Classic. In contrast, the themes addressed by men tend to reach higher MNCS and usually are more related to computer science. In fact, typically, the geometric mean of citation and the percentage of documents in the computed indicators reached by these themes are higher than for the themes covered by women. Therefore, the theme covered by each gender suggests that the difference in impact perceived by women and men researchers may be affected by the theme addressed. This aspect can be observed in the *Covid-19* theme when documents produced by male authors perceive a higher MNCS than the documents produced by all genders. On the other hand, the theme *Smart city*, related to STEM and observed in the diagram in which most of the authors were female, suggests that women are involved in this production, and may achieve a higher impact than others. The findings of this research may be related to external factors, such as social aspects (Ceci et al., 2014; Kozlowski et al., 2022), career trajectory (Boekhout et al., 2021), collaboration (Yamamoto & Frachtenberg, 2022), and local of publication (Murray et al., 2018). To understand these aspects, future research should consider different variables in order to further demonstrate and extend what we have stated in this study.

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